

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 2.48

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.570104

DOI URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.570104>

Cite this paper as : Aman S & Jitendra S.B (2017). OPTIMAL PLACEMENT OF UNIFIED POWER FLOW CONTROLLER (UPFC) IN IEEE 14 BUS SYSTEM USING GENETIC ALGORITHM (GA), International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research, Volume 4,(Issue 2, Feb-Apr-2017), pp 15-30 . ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online), ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print), DOI URL <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.570104>

OPTIMAL PLACEMENT OF UNIFIED POWER FLOW CONTROLLER (UPFC) IN IEEE 14 BUS SYSTEM USING GENETIC ALGORITHM (GA)

Mr. Aman Sharma¹, Mr. Jitendra Singh Bhadoriya²

M.Tech Research Scholar [Power Electronics], Dept. of Electrical Engineering, SGI, Sikar, Raj., India¹
Assistant Professor, Dept. of Electrical Engineering, SGI, Sikar, Raj., India²

Abstract:

With the increasing size of power system, there is a thrust on finding the solution to maximize the utilization of existing system and to provide adequate voltage support. For this the flexibility of power is needed. Flexible AC transmission system (FACTS) if placed optimally can be effective in providing voltage support, controlling power flow and in turn resulting into lower losses.

The algorithm to find the optimal location of UPFC based on genetic algorithm has been developed. The effect of these devices on line flows and bus voltage profile has been studied by placing at random location and placing them optimally with optimal ratings dictated by genetic algorithm. The effectiveness of developed algorithm has been tested on 14-bus systems. In this work, a comparison of the effects of compensation of a Simplified multi-machine (two-machine system) power system by shunt/series connected FACTS controllers at optimal location using GA. The model procedure of enhance voltage stability and power flows capability of systems is illustrated. The study system is a simple example of multi-machine system, which is simulated in MATLAB/PSAT.

Keywords- UPFC(unified power flow controller),PSAT(Power system analysis toolbox), GA(Genetic Algorithm)

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing Industrialization, urbanization of life style has led to rising dependency on the electrical power. This has resulted into quick development of power systems. This quick development has resulted into few uncertainties. Power disruptions and individual power outages are one of the most important harms and affect the financial system of any country. In contrast to the rapid changes in technologies and the power required by these technologies,

transmission systems are being pushed to operate closer to their stability limits and at the same time reaching their thermal limits because the delivery of power have been increasing. The most important problems faced by power industries in establishing the match between supply and demand are:Transmission & Distribution; supply the electric demand without exceeding the thermal limit. In large power system, problems causing power disruptions and blackouts leading to huge losses.

These constraints change the value of power delivered. However, these constraints can be suppressed by enhancing the power system control. One of the best methods for reducing these constraints is FACTS devices.

With the rapid increase of power electronics, *Flexible AC Transmission Systems* (FACTS) devices have been planned and implemented in power systems. FACTS devices can be utilized to manage power flow and enhance scheme stability. Mostly with the deregulation of the electricity advertise, there is a rising attention in using FACTS devices in the operation and control of power systems. A superior utilization of the existing power systems to raise their capacities and controllability by installing FACTS devices becomes crucial. FACTS devices are price effective alternatives to fresh transmission line construction [1].

Reactive power compensation is provided to reduce power transmission losses, to keep power transmission capability and to keep the supply voltage. Series compensation is managing of line impedance of a transmission line; with the modify of impedance of a line either inductive or capacitive compensation can be obtained thus facilitating active power transfer or control. Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC) is a combined series-shunt compensator and is connected in both modes with the transmission line to increase the power transfer capability, recover transient stability, decrease transmission losses and dampen power system oscillations. Shunt compensation is used to increase the steady-state transmittable power and to control the voltage profile along the line. Its combination of SSSC and STATCOM and its one of the most important members of FACTS family that are increasingly being applied to long transmission lines by the value in modern power systems. They can have different applications concerned with operation and manage of power system, such as arrangement power flow; decreasing unsymmetrical components damping the power oscillations and enhancing transient stability.

II. Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC)

Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC) is “A combination of Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) and a Static Synchronous Series Compensator (SSSC) as shown in Fig.1 which are coupled via a common DC link to allow bi-directional flow of real power between the series output terminals of the SSSC and the shunt output terminals of the STATCOM; and are controlled to provide concurrent real and reactive series line compensation without an external electric energy source.”

Fig. 1 Basic Structure of UPFC

The series inverter is controlled to inject a symmetrical three phase voltage system (V_c), of controllable magnitude and phase angle in series with the line to control active and reactive power flows on the transmission line. So, this inverter will exchange active and reactive power with the line. The reactive power is electronically provided by the series inverter, and the active power is transmitted to the dc terminals. The shunt inverter is operated in such a way as to demand this dc terminal power (positive or negative) from the line keeping the voltage across the storage capacitor V_{dc} constant. So, the net real power absorbed from the line by the UPFC is equal only to the losses of the inverters and their transformers. The remaining capacity of the shunt inverter can be used to exchange reactive power with the line so to provide a voltage regulation at the connection point. The two VSI's can work independently of each other by separating the dc side. So in that case, the shunt inverter is operating as a STATCOM (Static Synchronous Compensators) that generates or absorbs reactive power to regulate the voltage magnitude at the connection point. Instead, the series inverter is operating as SSSC (Static Synchronous series compensators) that generates or absorbs reactive power to regulate the current flow, and hence the power flows on the transmission line.

III. GENETIC ALGORITHM

Genetic Algorithm is one of the Evolutionary Algorithms search technique. The method was developed by John Holland. Genetic Algorithms are global search techniques based on the mechanism of natural selection and genetics. They can search several possible solutions simultaneously and produces high quality solutions. The goal of optimization is to find out the best optimal location of UPFC in power system using genetic algorithm [5].

In general the genetic algorithm follows the following steps:

Step1: Generate an initial population of binary string.

Step2: Calculate fitness value of each member of population based on the problem type (minimization or maximization).

Step3: Generate offspring string through reproduction, crossover and mutation and evaluate.

Step4: Calculate fitness value for each string.

Step5: Terminate the process if required solution is obtained or number of generation is attained.

The above process is represented in flow chart as shown in Fig.2

Fig. 2 Flow Chart for Genetic Algorithm

3.1 Fitness Function Calculation

After initialization, the fitness is evaluated for everyone of the population. The fitness is measure to of quality which is used to compare different solutions In general, a fitness function $F(x)$ is first derived from the objective function and used in successive genetic operations, and here objective function is loss minimization as given by eqn. (3.21). For minimization problems, the fitness function is an equivalent maximization problem chosen such that the optimum point remains unchanged. The following fitness function for loss minimization problems can be expressed as:

$$F(X) = \frac{1}{1+F_l} \quad (3.1)$$

As it is easy to find the maximum value of objective function using GA, so inverse function is selected to convert the objective function into a maximum one.

3.2 Reproduction

Reproduction is a process where the individual is selected to move to a new generation according to its fitness. In reproduction process the fittest individual is selected. The various methods to select individuals are Roulette-wheel selection, Boltzmann selection, Tournament selection and Rank selection. In this problem formulation Roulette-wheel selection criterion is used.

Each individual in the population has its interval. The size of each interval corresponds to the fitness of the individual and can be defined as:

$$P_i = \frac{F_i}{\sum F_i} \quad (3.2)$$

Where

P_i = probability for selecting i th string.

F_i = the fitness of i th individual.

To select an individual, a random number is generated in the interval and the individual whose segment spans the random number is selected. The probability of an individual's reproduction is proportional to its fitness.

3.3 Crossover

Crossover is applied after reproduction; purpose of crossover is to exchange information among the strings of mating pool to create new strings.

Prime distinguished factor of GA from other optimization techniques. Two individuals are chosen from the population using the selection operator. A crossover site along the bit strings is randomly chosen. The values of the two strings are exchanged up to this point. If $S_1=000000$ and $S_2=111111$ and the crossover point is 2 then $S_1'=110000$ and $S_2'=001111$. The two new offspring created from this mating are put into the next generation of the population. By recombining portions of good individuals, this process is likely to create even better individuals.

Crossover rate p_c is the probability of crossover and varies from 0 to 1. Typically crossover rates vary from 0.7 to 1 for a population of 30 to 200.

3.4 Mutation

Mutation is used to introduce some sort of diversification in the population to avoid premature convergence to local optimum. Mutation involves just flipping of the bit for binary structure i.e. 1 to 0 or 0 to 1 and alteration of number in case of real value structure.

Mutation rate is the probability of mutation. Mutation helps in preserving lost information to the population. Typically mutation rate varies from 0.001 to 0.5 for a population size of 30 to 200.

The steps to optimally locate UPFC with Genetic Algorithm are as follows:

Step 1: Read system data.

Step 2: Run load flow using Newton Raphson method to find losses in the system.

Step 3: Assume suitable population size, maximum number of generation.

Step 4: Set counter =0.

Step 5: Randomly generate chromosomes.

Step 6: Modify values with the help of randomly generated values.

Step 7: Run load flow with modified values for each generating pattern. Calculate losses using eq. (3.21) and evaluate fitness value.

Step 8: Increment counter i.e. counter= counter +1

Step 9: Select new population using Roulette-wheel selection criterion as detailed in section 4.2.4.

Step 10: Perform crossover and evaluate objective function.

Step 11: Perform mutation and evaluate objective function and add off-springs generated by crossover and mutation to the population generated by selection and replace initial population.

Step 12: Repeat this process until convergence is achieved or maximum number of generation is reached.

IV. OBJECTIVE FUNCTION

As the main objective of this work is to determine the optimal location of the FACTS devices UPFC in the power network to minimize the losses (both active and reactive power loss), the following performance index is selected:

$$\min F_l = \sum_{k=1}^{ntl} S_{Ltl} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\min F_l = \sum_{k=1}^{ntl} P_{Ltl} + jQ_{Ltl} \quad (4.2)$$

Where

F_l is the objective function to minimize power losses.

P_{Ltl} is the active power loss in tl^{th} line.

Q_{Ltl} is the reactive power loss in tl^{th} line.

S_{Ltl} is the overall apparent power loss in tl^{th} line.

ntl is the number of transmission lines in the system.

Subjected to constraints:

$$P_{Gi}^{min} \leq P_{Gi} \leq P_{Gi}^{max} \quad (4.3)$$

$$Q_{Gi}^{min} \leq Q_{Gi} \leq P_{Gi}^{max} \quad (4.4)$$

$$V_i^{min} \leq V_i \leq V_i^{max} \quad (4.5)$$

$$|S_{Ltl}| \leq S_{Gi}^{max} \quad (4.6)$$

$$0 \leq V_{FDi} \leq V_{FDi}^{max} \quad (4.7)$$

$$Q_{FDi}^{\min} \leq Q_{FDi} \leq P_{FDi}^{\max} \quad (4.8)$$

Where,

P_{Gi}, Q_{Gi} : real and reactive power generations at bus i ,

P_{Di}, Q_{Di} : real and reactive loads at bus i ,

V_i, V_j : voltage magnitudes at bus i and j ,

$P_{FDi}(V_{FDi}, \alpha_{FDi})$: injected real power of FACTS (UPFC) device at bus i ,

$Q_{FDi}(V_{FDi}, \alpha_{FDi})$: injected reactive power of FACTS (UPFC) device at bus i ,

S_{Li} : i th line or transformer loading,

V. IMPLEMENTATION OF TEST SYSTEM

In this work, we have presented the load flow simulation results of the 14-bus Power System using PSAT, an advanced open source Power System Analysis Toolbox.

5.1 Introduction of PSAT (Power System Analysis Toolbox)

The Power System Analysis Toolbox (PSAT), an open source MATLAB and GNU/Octave-based software package for analysis and design of small to medium size electric power systems. PSAT includes power flow, continuation power flow, optimal power flow, small-signal stability analysis, and time-domain simulation, as well as several static and dynamic models, including nonconventional loads, synchronous and asynchronous machines, regulators, and FACTS. PSAT is also provided with a complete set of user-friendly graphical interfaces and a Simulink-based editor of one-line network diagrams. Basic features, algorithms, and a variety of case studies are presented in this paper to illustrate the capabilities of the presented tool and its suitability for educational and research purposes.

5.2 14-Bus system modeling and implementation

This section illustrates the modeling and implementation of the 14-bus test system, which is given below. The all input data of system first converted in per unit values based on its base value. Fig. 5.3 depicts the model of the IEEE 14-bus network built using the PSAT Simulink library. Once defined in the Simulink model, one can load the network in PSAT and solve the power flow. Power flow results can be displayed in a GUI (see Fig.5.1) and exported to a file in several formats including Excel and LaTeX. PSAT also allows displaying bus voltages and power flows within the Simulink model of the currently loaded system.

Fig. 5.1: Executing the PSAT in GUI Mode

Fig. 5.2. IEEE 14-bus test system

Fig.5.3. PSAT-Simulink model of the IEEE 14-bus test system

VI. RESULT ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the results obtained on the performance of power system with the placement of UPFC. The installation of UPFC has been studied for their placement at arbitrary location and optimal location decided by GA. The performance has been studied on 14-bus systems the data used for these case studies is given in Appendix-1.

First, Newton-Raphson-Method is run without any FACTS devices with following parameters in PSAT are used:

Base MVA= 100.

And base Kv= 69 k

6.1 Comparative result analysis for the power system with and with-out UPFC

Table 6.1

Active Power flow (transfer) Comparison With and With-out UPFC of lines

From Bus	To Bus	Lines	P Flow with UPFC [p.u.]	P Flow with-out UPFC [p.u.]
Bus 02	Bus 05	1	0.73799	0.58278
Bus 06	Bus 12	2	0.1165	0.11726
Bus 12	Bus 13	3	0.02943	0.03017
Bus 06	Bus 13	4	0.27001	0.27313
Bus 06	Bus 11	5	0.1384	0.14449
Bus 11	Bus 10	6	0.08654	0.09253
Bus 09	Bus 10	7	0.04074	0.0348
Bus 09	Bus 14	8	0.10776	0.104
Bus 14	Bus 13	9	-0.1023	-0.106
Bus 07	Bus 09	10	0.46209	0.45586
Bus 01	Bus 02	11	1.3187	2.415
Bus 03	Bus 02	12	-1.0502	-1.0003
Bus 03	Bus 04	13	-0.2686	-0.3185
Bus 01	Bus 05	14	0.7704	1.1056
Bus 05	Bus 04	15	0.66226	0.81253
Bus 02	Bus 04	16	0.89249	0.77808
Bus 04	Bus 09	17	0.09945	0.09598
Bus 05	Bus 06	18	0.68171	0.69168
Bus 04	Bus 07	19	0.46209	0.45586
Bus 08	Bus 07	20	0	0

Fig. 6.1 Active Power flow (transfer) Comparison With and With-out UPFC

The table 6.1 and figure 6.1 Shows Active Power flow (transfer) Comparison With and With-out UPFC of lines. It shows the comparative analysis of Active Power flow Transfer for with and with-out UPFC condition. So the analysis denotes the Active Power flow Transfer with UPFC of lines is reduced at high power flow lines so the Active Power Transfer capability of system is increased.

Table 6.2

Reactive Power flow (transfer) Comparison With and With-out UPFC of lines

From Bus	To Bus	Lines	Q Flow with UPFC [p.u.]	Q Flow with-out UPFC [p.u.]
Bus 02	Bus 05	1	0.03313	0.07227
Bus 06	Bus 12	2	0.04493	0.04464
Bus 12	Bus 13	3	0.01905	0.01873
Bus 06	Bus 13	4	0.14225	0.14163
Bus 06	Bus 11	5	0.12341	0.12199
Bus 11	Bus 10	6	0.09224	0.09057
Bus 09	Bus 10	7	-0.008	-0.0063
Bus 09	Bus 14	8	0.00893	0.01006

Bus 14	Bus 13	9	-0.0642	-0.0628
Bus 07	Bus 09	10	0.23088	0.23268
Bus 01	Bus 02	11	0.56075	-0.3802
Bus 03	Bus 02	12	0.16181	0.13866
Bus 03	Bus 04	13	0.16864	0.1933
Bus 01	Bus 05	14	0.11205	0.10122
Bus 05	Bus 04	15	-0.0772	-0.1384
Bus 02	Bus 04	16	0.02951	0.05165
Bus 04	Bus 09	17	0.03569	0.03594
Bus 05	Bus 06	18	0.07926	0.07613
Bus 04	Bus 07	19	-0.0495	-0.0501
Bus 08	Bus 07	20	0.34101	0.34242

Fig. 6.2 Reactive Power flow (transfer) Comparison With and With-out UPFC

The table 6.2 and figure 6.2 Shows Reactive Power flow (transfer) Comparison With and With-out UPFC of lines. It shows the comparative analysis of Reactive Power flow Transfer for with and with-out UPFC condition. So the analysis denotes the Reactive Power flow Transfer with UPFC of lines is reduced at high power flow lines so the Reactive Power Transfer capability of system is increased and the Reactive power consumption is reduces hence availability increased.

Table 6.3

Voltage magnitude profile Comparison With and With-out UPFC at buses

Bus no.	V With-out UPFC	V With UPFC
1	1.06	1.06
2	1.045	1.045
3	1.01	1.01
4	0.99772	0.99795
5	1.0024	1.0034
6	1.07	1.07
7	1.0347	1.0349
8	1.09	1.09
9	1.0111	1.0115
10	1.0105	1.0109
11	1.0346	1.0349
12	1.0461	1.0461
13	1.0362	1.0363
14	0.99568	0.9968

Fig. 6.3 Voltage magnitude profile Comparison With and With-out UPFC at buses

The table 6.3 and figure 6.3 Shows Voltage magnitude profile Comparison With and With-out UPFC at buses. It shows the comparative analysis of Voltage profile for with and with-out UPFC condition. So the analysis denotes Voltage profile with UPFC of lines is enhanced at buses hence the Voltage profile of system is increased.

CONCLUSION

The work on ‘Evolutionary Algorithm assisted Optimal Placement of FACTS Controllers in Power System’ has been carried out to find optimal location of UPFC to improve the voltage profile, reduce losses and enhancement in power system transfer capability of the system. The optimal placement of FACTS controllers has been attempted using Genetic Algorithm. The study has been carried out on 14-bus system. From the study following conclusions are drawn.

- The developed algorithm is effective in deciding the placement of FACTS devices.
- UPFC helps in diverting flow from heavily loaded lines and results in reduction in active power losses.
- UPFC helps in improving voltage profile of the system and results in reduced reactive power losses.
- UPFC enhanced overall power system transfer capability of the system and results in reduced overall power losses.

REFERENCES

- [1] Azimoh L.C and Folly K.A ‘Mitigations of Voltage Instability in Power Systems’, Electrical Power and Energy Conference, University of Cape Town, South Africa,IEEE (2009).
- [2] Gupta Vibhor, ‘Study and Effects of UPFC and its Control System for Power Flow Control and Voltage Injection in a Power System’ International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology Vol. 2(7), 2010, 2558-2566 (2010).
- [3] Jahani R. “Optimal Placement of Unified Power Flow Controller in Power System Using Imperialist Competitive Algorithm” Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research 8 (6): 999-1007, 2011, ISSN 1990-9233 © IDOSI Publications, pp. 999-1007, (2011).
- [4] Kalaivaniand R., Kamaraj V. ‘Modeling of Shunt FACTS Devices for Voltage Stability Enhancement’ European Journal of Scientific Research ISSN 1450-216X Vol.61 No.1 (2011), pp. 144-154, EuroJournals Publishing, Inc. (2011)
- [5] Kazemi A., Vahidinasab V., Mosallanejad A. ‘Study of STATCOM and UPFC Controllers for Voltage Stability Evaluated by Saddle-Node Bifurcation Analysis’ First International Power and Energy Conference PECon, 2006, Putrajaya, Malaysia 28-29 November (2006).
- [6] Lee K. Y. "Dynamic and Static Voltage Stability Enhancement of Power Systems," IEEE Transactions on Power Systems, Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 231-238, (1993)
- [7] Marouani Ismail, Guesmi Tawfik, Hadj Abdallah Hsen, “Optimal Location of Multi Type FACTS Devices for Multiple Contingencies Using Genetic Algorithms”, International Journal of Energy Engineering, Vol. 2(2), pp. 29-35,(2012).
- [8] North American Electric Reliability Council (NERC) report ‘Available Transfer Capability Definitions and Determination’ June (1996).

- [9] Padiyar K. R. and Devi A. L. "Control and simulation of static condenser," in Proc. 9th Annu. Applied Power Electronics Conf. Expo., Feb. 13-17 (1994).
- [10] Sarda Jigar S., Parmar Vibha N., Patel Dhaval G., Patel Lalit K. 'Genetic Algorithm Approach for Optimal location of FACTS devices to improve system loadability and minimization of losses' International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Vol. 1, Issue 3, pp.114-125(2012).
- [11] Sreejaya P., Rejitha R. 'Reactive power and Voltage Control in Kerala Grid and Optimization of Control Variables Using Genetic Algorithm', IEEE, pp. 243-248 (2008).
- [12] Stéphane Gerbex, Rachid Cherkaoui, and Alain J. Germond "Optimal Location of Multi-Type FACTS Devices in a Power System by Means of Genetic Algorithms", IEEE Tra. On power system, VOL. 16, NO. 3, pp. 537-544 (2001).
- [13] Venkateswarlu K., Saibabu Ch. "A New Evolutionary Algorithms Used For Optimal Location Of Upfc On Power System" Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, JATIT & LLS, pp. 107-118(2010).
- [14] Mishra Pushpendra, h. N. Udupa, piyushghune, "Calculation of Sensitive Node for IEEE – 14 Bus System when Subjected to Various Changes in Load" Proceedings of IRAJ International Conference, Pune, India, pp.89-92 (2013).
- [15] Hingorani N.g. "High power Electronics and Flexible AC Transmission System," IEEE Power Eng. REV(1998).
- [16] Proposed terms and definitions for flexible AC transmission system (FACTS), " Power Delivery, IEEE Transactions on , vol.12, no.4, pp.1848,1853, doi: 10.1109/61.634216(1997).
- [17] Jahani R. H.A. Shayanfar N. M. Tabatabaei J. Olamaei "optimal placement of unified power flow controller in power system by a new advanced heuristic method" International Journal on "Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering" issue 5 volume 2 Number 4 pg(2010).
- [18] R Kalaivani, Kamaraj V "Enhancement of Voltage Stability by Optimal Location of Static Var Compensator Using Genetic Algorithm and Particle Swarm Optimization" American J. of Engineering and Applied Sciences 5 (1): 70-77, ISSN 1941-7020(2012).
- [19] T.Nireekshana Dr.G.Kesava Rao Dr.S.Siva Naga Raju "Incorporation of Unified Power Flow Controller Model for Optimal Placement using Particle Swam Optimization Technique" 978-1-4244-8679-3/11 IEEE(2011).
- [20] Nor Rul Hasma Abdullah, Ismail Musirin and Muhammad Murtadha Othman "Transmission Loss Minimization and UPFC Installation Cost using Evolutionary Computation for Improvement of Voltage Stability" Proceedings of the 14th International Middle East Power Systems Conference (MEPCON'10), Cairo University, Egypt, Paper ID 293(2010).
- [21] Jigar S.Sarda, Manish J. Chauhan, Viren B. Pandya, International Journal of Research in Computer Science ISSN 2249-8265 Volume 2 Issue 3 pp. 11-15(2012)

- [22] Ghanaati Omid, Seirafian Vahid Reza, Naderpour Iman, Teymouri Jalal “Power System Security Improvement with Optimal Placement of FACTS Devices Using Genetic Algorithms” International Conference on Computer Applications and Industrial Electronics(2011).
- [23] D. E. Goldberg, “Genetic Algorithms in Search optimization and Machine Learning”, Addison-Wesley publishers, (1999).
- [24] N.G. Hingorani and L.Gyugi , “Understanding FACTS –Concepts and Technology of Flexible Ac Transmission Systems”, Standard Publishers Distributors, IEEE Press, New York, (2001).
- [25] Padiyar K.R. “FACTS Controllers in power transmission and distribution”,New Age International Publishers, (2007).
- [26] Y. H .Song and A. T. Johns, Flexible AC Transmission System, IEEE Press London, (1999).
- [27] A. Mosallanejad. "Study of STATCOM, UPFC and facts Controllers for Voltage Stabilityby Saddle-Node Bifurcation Analysis" IEEE International Power and Energy Conference, Nov. (2006).
- [28] Agnihotri, Ganga, Manisha Dubey, and AASHISH BOHRE "Optimal Sizing and Sitting of DG with Load Models using Soft Computing Techniques in Practical Distribution System", IET Generation Transmission & Distribution, (2016).
- [29] T.N.P. Nambiar. "Development of a Laboratory Model of Hybrid Static VAR Compensator", IEEE Power India Conference, (2006).
- [30] Dutta ,Susanta, Provas Kumar Roy, and Debashis Nandi. "Optimal location of UPFC controller in transmission network using hybrid chemical reaction optimization algorithm", International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems, (2015).